

Comparative evaluation of monocular deep learning pose estimation and IMU-based systems for remote kinematic assessment

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Introduction

Remote assessment of human motion is increasingly pivotal in clinical [1], sports [2], and rehabilitation contexts, particularly given the rise of telemedicine. While traditional motion capture systems deliver high-precision data, their dependence on expensive equipment and controlled laboratory conditions limits their broader application [3]. Advances in deep learning and computer vision have enabled the development of monocular video-based 3D human pose estimation methods, which leverage ubiquitous camera technologies to offer cost-effective and accessible kinematic analysis [4]. This study systematically benchmarks joint angles derived from both video-based models and IMUs, addressing the gap in comparative evaluations under realistic, out-of-the-lab conditions.

Research Question

Does the kinematics extracted from video-based pose estimation models match that of inertial sensors in capturing clinically relevant joint angles during everyday activities?

Methods

Video recordings and IMU data collected from 16 subjects performing 5 daily-life activities from VIDIMU dataset [5] was used to evaluate representative movements with clinical relevance. Joint angles were computed from the video-derived 3D keypoints. Then, the pipeline converted model outputs into a unified format, applied interpolation and smoothing filters to mitigate noise, and synchronized the time-series data with the reference IMU joint signals extracted from OpenSim [6]. To quantify the accuracy of the video-based estimations, two metrics were computed: RMSE to assess the magnitude of the deviations between both modalities, and Pearson Correlation Coefficient to evaluate the linear relationship between them. These metrics were calculated separately for each of the five selected activities, thereby providing a focused comparison of performance across diverse movement tasks.

Results

In the analysis of five upper- and lower-limb selected tasks, performance varied across models. For *walk_forward*, MMPose [7] achieved the lowest RMSE of 6.54° and highest correlation coefficient of 0.88. In *walk_along* and *move_right_arm*, MotionAGFormer [8] excelled, recording error values of 5.98° and 6.14° with correlations of 0.90 and 0.92, respectively. In the *drink_left_arm* task, although BodyTrack [9]

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had the best correlation of 0.97, MotionBERT [10] delivered the smallest RMSE of 8.39°. For *tear_both_arms*, MotionAGFormer showed the lowest error 4.99° and highest correlation 0.98.

Discussion

Our findings highlight that model performance is intrinsically linked to task dynamics and architectural design. MotionAGFormer’s hybrid design, merging transformer-based global context with GCN-driven local refinement, excels in capturing complex movements, while sequential lifting methods like MMPose perform better in steadier, predictable tasks. While MotionBERT is trained to recover 3D motion representations from noisy 2D inputs, it may inadequately generalize to fine-grained joint kinematics in dynamic tasks. These trade-offs in accessibility, inference speed, and performance emphasize the need to select models aligned with specific clinical applications. Additionally, our work affirms the viability of video-based approaches as accessible, non-intrusive and cost-effective alternatives to IMUs for kinematic assessment in real-world telerehabilitation.

Table 1. Per-activity mean and standard deviation of RMSE and PCC across all models

Root Mean Square Error (RMSE)					
ID	Legend	MotionAGFormer	MotionBERT	MMPose	BodyTrack
A01	<i>walk_forward</i>	8.12 ± 3.42	7.40 ± 2.56	<u>6.54 ± 2.64</u>	7.07 ± 2.73
A03	<i>walk_along</i>	<u>5.66 ± 2.72</u>	7.09 ± 2.54	6.25 ± 2.61	6.02 ± 2.26
A05	<i>move_right_arm</i>	<u>6.14 ± 2.64</u>	13.47 ± 3.90	10.19 ± 2.70	13.02 ± 3.02
A08	<i>drink_left_arm</i>	8.94 ± 3.21	<u>8.39 ± 3.14</u>	8.49 ± 2.62	8.40 ± 2.97
A13	<i>tear_both_arms</i>	<u>4.99 ± 2.48</u>	16.79 ± 6.42	17.57 ± 3.53	7.61 ± 2.55

Pearson Correlation Coefficient (PCC)					
ID	Legend	MotionAGFormer	MotionBERT	MMPose	BodyTrack
A01	<i>walk_forward</i>	0.83 ± 0.12	0.87 ± 0.10	<u>0.88 ± 0.11</u>	0.87 ± 0.12
A03	<i>walk_along</i>	<u>0.92 ± 0.06</u>	0.89 ± 0.07	0.90 ± 0.06	0.91 ± 0.05
A05	<i>move_right_arm</i>	<u>0.92 ± 0.06</u>	0.79 ± 0.11	0.87 ± 0.06	0.64 ± 0.19
A08	<i>drink_left_arm</i>	0.91 ± 0.13	0.94 ± 0.06	0.93 ± 0.05	<u>0.97 ± 0.02</u>
A13	<i>tear_both_arms</i>	<u>0.98 ± 0.02</u>	0.88 ± 0.10	0.93 ± 0.05	0.94 ± 0.06

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